

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**Estimation of the Global Solar Radiation in Anyigba Kogi State Using Hargreaver And Samani**Ayodele S. Abdullateef*¹, Ohiani O. Alexander¹, Adeyemi O. John¹. Papa M.A¹

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Abstract

This work estimates the global solar radiation in Anyigba with latitude 7.498 using Hargreaves and Samani model. The average monthly global radiation for Anyigba was found to be 32 MJ/m² /day with a MBE of 15.6333 MJ/m² /day and RMSE OF 5.985 MJ/m² /day.

Keywords: Hargreave and Samani; Global Solar Radiation; Extraterrestrial Solar Radiation; Clear Sky Index

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1.Introduction

Having adequate information of the global solar radiation and other meteorological factors is important both in the field of solar energy and agriculture. Empirical models such as Angstrom-PreScott and Hargreaves and Samani model can be used to estimate global solar radiation. This is because many locations in developing countries do not have weather stations that record this meteorological factors such as temperature, humidity and global solar radiation (Abdu and Ayodele, 2016).

Solar radiation data is important in architectural design, solar energy design and irrigation system and crop growth (Okogbue and Adedokun, 2002). Most empirical models uses sunshine meteorological factor for the estimation of global solar radiation (Abdu and Ayodele, 2016). Temperature factor based models like Hargreaves and samani can also be used were temperature data is available.

Some related work includes the research conducted by Bernadetta, *et al* 2017, which involves testing of the performance of some empirical models. The model tested includes Garcia's model. This research was conducted in Makurdi using weather data between 1990-1991 and 1995 to 2003 (Jegede *et al*, 2017) where the global solar radiation month variation for the location was estimated.

Ayegba *et al*, used Hargreaves and Samani model to estimate the global solar radiation for Abuja using minimum and maximum temperature data between February 1-29, 2016, obtained from weather online limited . The maximum global radiation was estimated to be 29.60.609 MJ/m² / day.

Jegede *et al* 2017, estimated the monthly global solar radiation on Ida campus of Ida Federal polytechnic in Kogi State using maximum and minimum temperature data between July 1998 to June 30, 2015. It was observed that Hargreaves and Samani's model has their values of maximum global solar radiation more than Angstrom model's estimated global solar radiation. Therefore there is need to extend the use of Hargreaves and samani model beyond Ida and ascertain its suitability for other locations.

Aim

Aim of this study is to evaluate the global solar radiation in Anyigba, Kogi state, using Hargreaves and Samani Model, by obtaining the solar radiation data from the Centre for Atmospheric Research, determine the variability of solar radiation in Anyigba using Hargreaves and Samani then have better understanding of how solar radiation changes in different months of the year using this model.

Scope of the study

This study will be carried out in the geographical area of Anyigba with altitude of 420metres above